

The Effect of Leadership and Work Environment on Work Satisfaction with Motivation as Intervening Variables in PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV)

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to: 1) analyze the influence of leadership and work environment on motivation 2) analyze the influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction, 3) analyze the influence of motivation on job satisfaction, 4) analyze the influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction through motivation. The research was conducted at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) with a sample of 92 employees. The sampling technique used simple random sampling technique. Methods of data analysis using descriptive analysis and path analysis.

The results show that: 1) there is an influence of leadership and work environment on motivation, 2) there is an influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction, 3) there is an effect of motivation on job satisfaction, 4) motivation does not play a role in improving leadership and work environment on job satisfaction at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV).

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Work Environment, Motivation, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the national television broadcasting service industry is getting tougher these days. Eleven television stations broadcast nationally, plus network television and local television in each provincial city and level two regions, as well as cable television broadcasts. This illustrates the dynamics of the television industry, which essentially wants to gain financial benefits from the increasing total television advertising spending. One of the television broadcasting service companies that took part in the competition was PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV).

Based on the monitoring results of PT Sigi Kaca Pariwara (Adstensity), MNCTV is in sixth position with advertising revenue of Rp9.29 trillion, down from 2017 in fifth position with revenues of Rp10.97 trillion. The first position is occupied by Antv with advertising revenue of Rp. 15.66 trillion, an increase compared to 2017 in the third position with revenue of Rp. 11.90 trillion. The second is Global TV with Rp13.78 trillion in revenue, the third is Indosiar Rp.12.90 trillion, the fourth is Kompas TV is Rp.12.78 trillion, and the fifth is Metro TV is Rp. 12.3 trillion.

This increasingly fierce competition forces PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV) to be able to deal with any changes that occur with the various resources it has. The most important resource for a company or organization is human resources, namely people who have given their energy, talent, creativity and effort to the organization (Handoko, 2001: 133). Likewise with PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV), success in managing its human resources will determine the success of achieving organizational goals, namely winning the competition.

Job satisfaction has a considerable influence on organizational performance either directly or indirectly. Hasibuan (2003:203) reveals, "A person tends to work with enthusiasm if satisfaction can be obtained from his work, and employee job satisfaction becomes a morale, discipline, and employee performance boost in supporting the realization of company goals. Meanwhile, dissatisfaction will be the beginning of problems that arise. Arise in the company, such as absenteeism, conflict between managers and workers, and employee turnover. Dissatisfaction also causes a decrease in motivation, and work performance both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Job satisfaction is a reflection of employee attitudes towards their work. According to Munandar (2001: 357) job satisfaction is influenced by several factors, namely job characteristics, salary, supervision, supportive colleagues and supportive working conditions. Increasing employee job satisfaction in an organization cannot be separated from the role of leaders in the

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organization, leadership is the main key in management which plays an important and strategic role in the survival of a company, leaders are the originators of goals, planners, people who organize, move and control all resources owned so that organizational goals can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

The company is a business organization consisting of people, so the leader should be able to align individual needs with organizational needs based on human relations (Robbins, 2001:18). In line with that, it is hoped that a leader will be able to motivate and create social conditions that benefit each employee, so that employee job satisfaction is achieved, which has implications for increasing employee productivity.

The importance of employee job satisfaction in a company, it is appropriate if a company pays attention to aspects related to employee job satisfaction. According to Griffin (2007: 122), there is a two-factor theory which states that job satisfaction and employee performance are influenced by motivational factors such as recognition of work that has been completed well and environmental factors such as workplace conditions.

The role of a leader is very influential on his leadership in an organization. If the leadership is good, the service will also be good, but if the leadership is not good, it will cause fear, laziness, hatred and lack of enthusiasm for the subordinates they lead. Seen from any point of view, the leader is always placed in an organization or group is very vital. Because in this role, a leader will help the organization to realize its vision and mission. Therefore, the effectiveness of a leader in using his influence will determine how the leader can play his role well. For this reason, the leader must always be honed and developed, so that he can adapt to the situations he faces. Whether the situation comes from subordinates, superiors or organizations. It can be seen here that the importance of a leader when carrying out his leadership can empower himself before empowering others.

In the realm of leadership there are three things that must be developed by a leader, namely a leader must be able to lead himself (managing self), lead people (managing people), and lead tasks (managing jobs). Effectiveness in carrying out leadership must start from oneself. There is no way a leader who fails to make himself effective will succeed in making other people or his work effective. Talking about personal effectiveness, like it or not, a leader must have the ability to determine the identification of his potential. The ability to identify this will provide a strong enough provision for a leader to develop himself. So that when the leadership role is temporarily carried out it does not only depend on the position but more because of the influences that come from his personal capacity.

An organization or company will succeed or even fail largely determined by leadership. A noble expression that says that the leader is responsible for the failure of the implementation of a job, is an expression that places the position of the leader in a government organization in the most important position. A leadership role that is very strategic and important for achieving the mission, vision and goals of a government organization, is one of the motives that encourage people to always investigate the intricacies associated with leadership. - earnestly to foster, mobilize, direct all potential employees in the environment in order to realize a goal-directed workload.

Based on the definition of leadership above, it can be interpreted that leadership is a person's ability to influence, move, encourage, control other people or their subordinates to do something work on their consciousness and contribute to achieving a goal.

Managerial leadership can be defined as a process of directing and influencing the activities of a group of members whose tasks are interconnected (Handoko, 2001: 291). Therefore, the leader of a company organization is required to always be able to create conditions that are able to satisfy employees at work so that employees are obtained who are not only able to work but are also willing to work towards achieving company goals.

Rivai (2004: 146) suggests "the work environment is an organizational element as a social system that has a strong influence on the formation of individual behavior in the organization and affects organizational performance". The work environment consists of two, namely the physical work environment and non-physical work environment. In simple terms it can be described, the physical work environment includes everything that is tangible and felt by employees such as equipment, supplies and office layout. Some examples are good spatial management, lighting, air exchange/ventilation, technology used, and noise level. The non-physical work environment in general can be described by a work atmosphere that is not physically visible, such as a sense of security at work, the relationship between leaders and subordinates, and fellow co-workers.

Organizations that have a regular and comfortable work environment both physically and non-physically will increase the motivation for their employees to improve performance. A conducive working environment will help employees reduce boredom and fatigue, so that they will gradually be able to improve employee performance and organizational performance.

In carrying out their daily work, every employee needs a good work environment. With a good work environment, employees will feel comfortable and enthusiastic in carrying out their duties. Meanwhile, an unfavorable work environment can

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lead to negative things such as low morale, high absenteeism, high error rates in the execution of work, high employee turnover rates, and so on.

This work environment issue needs serious attention because the situation and conditions of the work environment will affect the employee's work results on an ongoing basis. The work environment, such as: air circulation, lighting, cleanliness, security, relations between fellow employees, and the relationship between employees and their leaders can affect the creativity and job satisfaction of employees.

In addition, the factor that must also be a concern is the work motivation of the employees. If the employee's work motivation is good, then the employee's performance will also be good. According to Wursanto (2003:38), motivation is an impulse, desire, desire, and driving force that comes from humans to do or to do something. Stimulating employee motivation must be done to encourage the achievement of good performance because according to Griffin (2004:38), motivation is a factor that greatly determines performance.

Motivation is the process of giving work motives to employees so that they are willing to work for the achievement of company goals effectively and efficiently. The provision of work motives is contained in Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory which includes physiological needs, security needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs as stated by Sofyandi and Garniwa (2007:102). With the fulfillment of all needs or desires and expectations, employees will get satisfaction, and employees with high levels of satisfaction will automatically increase their performance. The growth of motivation in employees becomes the basic thing in the direction of the process of achieving goals in the form of achieving job satisfaction and optimal work performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Job Satisfaction

According to Hanggraeni (2012:14), suggests that job satisfaction or job statistics is defined as an individual's attitude towards his job, someone who has high job satisfaction will have a positive attitude towards his job. Vice versa. People who are dissatisfied (low job satisfaction) will have a negative attitude towards their work.

Handoko (2008: 193-194) argues that job satisfaction is an emotional state that is pleasant or unpleasant so that employees view their work. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his job. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything that is faced in the work environment.

Quoted by Pangabean (2004:129) suggests that in addition to the things mentioned above, job satisfaction is also relevant to performance appraisal, this means that:

- a. Job satisfaction is any treatment they receive at work, including satisfaction with job evaluations, selection of facilities and incentive benefits, or termination.
- b. Job satisfaction is not a single-dimensional concept, but a plural dimension, a person may feel satisfied with the other dimensions.

Sutrisno (2009:81) suggests that job satisfaction is closely related to the attitude of employees towards their own work, work situations, and cooperation between leaders and fellow employees. Wexley and Yuki (2003:129) suggest that job satisfaction is the way an employee feels about his job. Job satisfaction is a generalization of attitudes towards work based on various aspects of work. There are hundreds of job characteristics that an employee considers, but a group of job characteristics tends to be evaluated together in the same way.

The factors commonly used to measure job satisfaction according to Robbins (2008), namely:

- a. The work itself (work it self), which is the main source of satisfaction where the job provides interesting tasks, work that is not boring, opportunities to learn, opportunities to accept responsibility and progress for employees.
- b. Salary/wages, which is a multidimensional factor in job satisfaction. A number of wages or money received by employees becomes an assessment for satisfaction, where this can be seen as something that is considered appropriate and appropriate.
- c. Supervision, namely the leadership's ability to provide technical assistance and behavioral support. The first is employee-centred, measured by the degree to which the manager exerts personal interest and care for the employee. The second is the climate of participation or influence in decision-making that can affect the work of employees.
- d. Coworkers, namely the relationship between co-workers who are cooperative is the simplest source of job satisfaction. Working groups, especially cohesive teams, act as a source of support, comfort, advice, and assistance to the individual

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members of the group. When employees feel satisfied with their co-workers in the group, it will encourage employees to be enthusiastic about work.

2. Leadership

Leaders are the essence of management. This means that management will achieve its goals if there is a leader. This leadership style can only be implemented by a leader. A leader is someone who has leadership skills, has the ability to influence the stance/opinion of a person or group of people without asking the reasons. A leader is someone who actively makes plans, coordinates, conducts experiments and leads work to achieve common goals.

Principles as a paradigm consist of several main ideas based on personal leadership and attitudes and have a strong influence on building themselves or the organization. Principle is part of a condition, realization and consequence. Perhaps the principle of creating trust and running as an unalterable compass/guide. The principle is a center or main source of life support systems that are displayed with 4 dimensions such as safety, guidance, wisdom, and strength (Covey, 2010: 47).

The characteristics of a leader are based on the following principles: A person who learns for life not only through formal education, but also outside of school. For example, learning through reading, writing, observation, and listening. Having good and bad experiences as a learning resource. Service-oriented, a leader is not served but served, because the principle of a leader with the principle of serving based on career as the main goal. In providing services, leaders should be more principled on good service. Bringing positive energy everyone has energy and enthusiasm. Using positive energy is based on sincerity and a desire to support the success of others. It takes positive energy to build good relationships. A leader must be able and willing to work for long periods of time and under unspecified conditions (Covey, 2010).

The indicators of leadership according to Martoyo (2000:176-179) include:

- a. Analytical Ability, The ability to analyze situations faced carefully, maturely, and steadily, is a prerequisite for the success of one's leadership.
- b. Communication Skills, In giving orders, instructions, guidelines, advice, a leader must master communication techniques.
- c. Courage, The higher a person's position in the organization he needs to have greater courage in carrying out the main tasks that have been entrusted to him.
- d. Listening Ability, One of the qualities that every leader needs to have is his ability and willingness to hear the opinions and or suggestions of others, especially his subordinates.
- e. Firmness, Assertiveness in dealing with subordinates and dealing with uncertainty, is very important for a leader.

3. Work Environment

The work environment is a factor that indirectly affects employee performance. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to work optimally. The work environment has a direct influence on employees in completing their responsibilities to the organization or company. If the employee likes the work environment in which he works, then the employee will feel at home in his workplace to carry out his activities and complete his duties or responsibilities.

The work environment includes working relationships that are formed between fellow employees, working relationships between subordinates and superiors, and the physical environment in a company or organization. According to Sedarmayanti (2001: 21) the physical work environment is all physical conditions that exist around the workplace that can affect employees either directly or indirectly. The physical work environment can be divided into two categories, namely:

- a. Environment that is directly related to employees (such as work centers, chairs, tables and so on)
- b. The intermediate environment or the general environment can also be called the work environment that affects the human condition, for example temperature, humidity, circulation, air, lighting, noise, unpleasant odors, colors and others.

According to Sedarmayanti (2009:28) the indicators of the work environment are as follows:

- a. Lighting/lighting in the workplace Light or lighting is very beneficial for employees in order to get safety and smooth work, therefore it is necessary to pay attention to the existence of lighting (light) that is bright but not dazzling. Light that is less clear (less enough) causes vision to become less clear, so work will be slow, experience many errors, and ultimately lead to less efficiency in carrying out work, so that organizational goals are difficult to achieve.
- b. Air circulation in the workplace Oxygen is a gas needed by living things to maintain survival, namely for metabolic processes. The surrounding air is said to be dirty if the oxygen level in the air has decreased and has been mixed with gases or odors that are harmful to the health of the body. The main source of fresh air is the presence of plants around the workplace.

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- c. Noise at work. One of the pollutions that is quite busy for experts to overcome is noise, which is sound that is not desired by the ear. Not desirable, because especially in the long term the sound can disturb the peace of work, damage hearing, and cause communication errors, even according to research, serious noise can cause death.
- d. Bad odors in the workplace, the presence of odors around the workplace can be considered as pollution, because it can interfere with concentration at work, and odors that occur continuously can affect olfactory sensitivity. The use of the right "air condition" is one way that can be used to eliminate disturbing odors around the workplace.
- e. Security in the workplace, in order to keep the place and conditions of the work environment safe, it is necessary to pay attention to safety at work. Therefore, the security factor needs to be realized. One of the efforts to maintain security in the workplace, can use the Security Officer Unit (SATPAM). From two different opinions, namely from Nitisemito (1992:159) and Sedarmayanti (2009:28) regarding the work environment, it is hoped that a conducive work environment will be created so that employees will feel at home at work. From two different opinions the researchers took indicators, namely work atmosphere, relationships with colleagues, availability of work facilities, lighting, air circulation, noise, unpleasant odors, and security.

4. Motivation

Motivation is a will or desire that arises in employees that creates enthusiasm or encouragement to work optimally in order to achieve goals. Motivation comes from the basic word motive, which has the meaning of a stimulus, desire and driving force of one's willingness to work. Motivation develops with a person's level of awareness of the goals to be achieved. Based on the explanation of the verse that achievement motivation does not always arise by itself. Motivation can be generated, developed and strengthened by other factors. The stronger a person's motivation, the stronger his efforts to achieve goals. This understanding also means that motivation can change.

Motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that employees want to work together effectively and are integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Motivation is the willingness to expend a high level of effort for organizational goals conditioned by the ability of that effort to meet some individual need. Needs occur when there is no balance between what is owned and what is expected. Encouragement is a mental force that is oriented towards fulfilling expectations and achieving goals. And goals are goals or things to be achieved by an individual.

According to McClelland in Hasibuan (2012:95) the dimensions of motivation:

- a. Need for achievement
- b. Need for affiliation
- c. Need for power

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Time

This research was carried out from August to November 2019. This research was carried out in stages: observation or interviews, making research proposals, making and testing research instruments, distributing questionnaires and analyzing research data. Researchers categorize into two stages, namely field research and data management and analysis.

Research Sites

This research was conducted at PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV) Tower 1, MNC Studios, Jl. Raya Perjuangan, Kebon Jeruk, West Jakarta City, DKI Jakarta.

Research Design

In this study to examine how much the contribution of the leadership variable, and the work environment as an independent variable (exogenous), motivation as a mediating variable (intervening) and job satisfaction as the dependent variable (endogenous). Intervening variables or variables that affect the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables are expressed in motivational variables. Then combined with relevant theories using data analysis techniques with reference to the variables used.

The collected data will be analyzed to determine the relationship or influence of the level of the independent variable which is influenced by the intervening variable on the dependent variable through path analysis. To support the statistical data acquisition process using the SPSS 23 application.

Method of Collecting Data

Sources of data in this study are primary data and secondary data.

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- a. Primary data is data collected directly by researchers to answer problems or research objectives. The research was carried out systematically by taking data in the field directly to respondents by filling out questionnaires. In this study, the data source is the user of PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV) employees. The score of the questionnaire was determined by using a Likert scale, namely the attitude of approval to the situation of the subject or object.
- b. Secondary data is data that has been collected by other parties not by the researchers themselves for other purposes. This means that researchers only record, access or request data as references such as books or similar research conducted by previous researchers.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2012:80) the population is a generalization area consisting of subjects who have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. In this study, the population taken was 1083 employees of PT Cipta TPI (MNCTV).

Nurdin and Hartati (2019: 95) say that the sample is a small part taken from members of the population based on a predetermined procedure so that it can be used to represent the population. Considering that the population in this study is quite large, this study takes a sample as a representative of the entire population. The sample in this study used a random sampling technique, meaning that the researcher took randomly from the total population. Based on Slovin's results, the sample of this study was 92 people (rounded up). So the research sample taken was 92 employees of PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Path Analysis

To test the effect of the mediating variable, the path analysis method was used. Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression analysis, or path analysis is the use of regression analysis to estimate causality relationships (causal models) between variables that have been previously determined based on theory (Ghozali, 2006: 210). Path analysis in this study can be described as follows:

1. Analysis of the Effect of Leadership and Work Environment on Motivation

According to Ghozali (2006: 211), the path coefficient uses standardized regression coefficients. The results of the regression analysis of the influence of leadership and work environment on motivation show the value of R2 (R Square) of 0.781. This R2 value is used in calculating the coefficient value of e1. The coefficient of e1 is a variant of motivation that is not explained by leadership and work environment.

$$\text{The coefficient } e_1 = \sqrt{(1 - R^2)} = \sqrt{(1 - 0,781)} = \sqrt{0,219} = 0,468 .$$

The results of the analysis can be seen the regression equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} X_3 &= b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e_1 \\ X_3 &= 0,075X_1 + 0,829X_2 + 0,468e_1 \dots\dots\dots (1) \end{aligned}$$

The equation shows that:

- Every 1 leadership increase will be followed by an increase in motivation of 0.075.
- Every 1 unit increase in work environment will be followed by an increase in motivation of 0.829.

So from equation (1) it can be seen that if the leadership is the motivation will increase. Likewise, the work environment increases, the motivation will increase.

2. Analysis of the Effect of Leadership, Work Environment, and Motivation on Job Satisfaction

The results of the regression analysis of the influence of leadership, work environment and motivation on job satisfaction show the R2 (R Square) value of 0.776. This R2 value is used in calculating the e2 coefficient value. The e2 coefficient is a variant of employee performance that is not explained by leadership, work environment and motivation.

$$\text{The coefficient } e_2 = \sqrt{(1 - R^2)} = \sqrt{(1 - 0,776)} = \sqrt{0,224} = 0,473 .$$

The results of the analysis can be seen the regression equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e_2 \\ Y &= 0,106X_1 + 0,250X_2 + 0,575X_3 + 0,473e_2 \dots\dots\dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

The equation shows that:

- Every time there is an increase in 1 leadership unit, it will be followed by an increase in job satisfaction of 0.106.
- Every 1 unit increase in the work environment will be followed by an increase in job satisfaction of 0.250.
- Every time there is an increase in 1 unit of motivation, it will be followed by an increase in job satisfaction of 0.575.

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So from equation (2) it can be seen that if the leadership is the job satisfaction will increase. If the work environment increases, job satisfaction will also increase. Likewise, if motivation increases, job satisfaction will also increase.

Hypothesis Testing

1. It is suspected that there is an influence of leadership and work environment on motivation

To find out this, it is necessary to use the F test. It is found that the F-count of the leadership and work environment variables is 158.574, while the F-table is 3.94. Thus $F\text{-count} > F\text{-Table}$. Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted at the real level. This gives the conclusion that leadership and work environment affect motivation. Thus the first hypothesis is tested and proven.

2. It is suspected that there is an influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction

To test the influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction, the F test was carried out. The F test results for the leadership style and motivation variables were 105.856 and the F-table was 3.94. $F\text{-count} > F\text{-table}$ which means H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This gives the conclusion that leadership and work environment affect job satisfaction. Thus the second hypothesis is tested and proven.

3. It is suspected that there is an influence of motivation on job satisfaction

To test the effect of motivation on work satisfaction, the t-test was carried out. The results of the t-test for the motivational variable obtained a t-count = 16,417 and a t-table of 1,663. This means that $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($16,417 > 1.663$), which means H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This gives the conclusion that motivation has an effect on job satisfaction. Thus the third hypothesis is tested and proven.

4. It is suspected that there is an influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction through motivation

$$X_1 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_1}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0.106 \times 0.250 = 0.027$$

$$X_2 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_2}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0.575 \times 0.250 = 0.143$$

In the leadership variable, the indirect influence value is obtained from the path coefficient value x_3x_1 multiplied by the path coefficient value yx_3 . The multiplication result shows that the value of the coefficient of indirect influence is smaller than the value of the coefficient of direct influence.

In the work environment variable, the indirect influence value is obtained from the path coefficient value x_3x_2 multiplied by the path coefficient value yx_3 . The multiplication result shows that the value of the coefficient of indirect influence is smaller than the value of the coefficient of direct influence. This shows that motivation cannot mediate, namely leadership and work environment in influencing job satisfaction. Thus the fourth hypothesis is not proven and tested.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Leadership and Work Environment on Motivation at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV)

Based on the description analysis on the leadership variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of analytical ability, communication skills, courage, listening ability and assertiveness make up the leadership variable. The indicator that dominates the formation of the leadership variable is the indicator of analytical ability, namely the MNCTV leadership has high organizational analysis skills. The work environment variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of lighting/light in the workplace, air circulation in the workplace, noise at work, unpleasant odors in the workplace, and safety at work make up the work environment variables. . The noise indicator in the workplace gives the greatest value to the formation of the work environment variable, namely the office where employees work far from vehicle noise. Likewise, the motivation variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree with the need for achievement, the need for affiliation and the need for power. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the motivational variable is the need for achievement, that is, all employees at MNCTV have a desire to excel in their work.

Based on the results of the regression analysis showed that leadership and work environment contributed to increasing employee motivation at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV). The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Ni Putu Intan Ratnasari, A.A. Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Deddy Novie Citra Arta, Harsono (2014); Deddy Novie Citra Arta, Harsono (2014); Ririn Puji Astutik (2017); Misdiana, Iranita, Roni Kurniawan (2017); Anak Agung Gede Dharma Saputra, Agoes Ganesha Rahyuda (2018).

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2. The Effect of Leadership and Work Environment on Job Satisfaction at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV)

Based on the description analysis on the leadership variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of analytical ability, communication skills, courage, listening ability and assertiveness make up the leadership variable. The indicator that dominates the formation of the leadership variable is the analytical ability indicator, namely the MNCTV leadership has high organizational analysis skills. The work environment variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of lighting/light in the workplace, air circulation at work, noise at work, unpleasant odors at work, and safety at work make up the work environment variables. . The noise indicator in the workplace gives the greatest value to the formation of the work environment variable, namely the office where employees work far from vehicle noise. The job satisfaction variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and co-workers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient.

Based on the results of the regression analysis showed that leadership and work environment contributed to increasing employee job satisfaction at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV). The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by I Gede Diatmika Paripurna (2017); Ni Putu Intan Ratnasari, A.A Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Anak Agung Gede Dharma Saputra, Agoes Ganesha Rahyuda (2018).

And it is not in line with the research of Devin Nelfan Tjandra, Meilinda Setiawati (2014); Deddy Novie Citra Arta, Harsono (2014); Ririn Puji Astutik (2017); Misdiana, Iranita, Roni Kurniawan (2017); Rini Astuti, Iverizkinawati (2018) and Yohana Putri Hapsari, Mahmud (2017).

3. The Effect of Motivation on Job Satisfaction at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV)

Based on descriptive analysis on motivational variables, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree with the need for achievement, the need for affiliation and the need for power. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the motivational variable is the need for achievement, that is, all employees at MNCTV have a desire to excel in their work. The job satisfaction variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and co-workers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient.

Based on the results of regression analysis shows that motivation contributes to increasing employee job satisfaction at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV). The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Devin Nelfan Tjandra, Meilinda Setiawati (2014); Ni Putu Intan Ratnasari, A.A Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Ririn Puji Astutik (2017); Dewi Suryani Harahap, Hazmanan Khair (2019); Anak Agung Gede Dharma Saputra, Agoes Ganesha Rahyuda (2018).

4. The Influence of Leadership and Work Environment on Job Satisfaction Through Motivation at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV)

Based on the description analysis on the leadership variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of analytical ability, communication skills, courage, listening ability and assertiveness make up the leadership variable. The indicator that dominates the formation of the leadership variable is the analytical ability indicator, namely the MNCTV leadership has high organizational analysis skills. The work environment variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of lighting/light in the workplace, air circulation at work, noise at work, unpleasant odors at work, and safety at work make up the work environment variables. . The noise indicator in the workplace gives the greatest value to the formation of the work environment variable, namely the office where employees work far from vehicle noise. The job satisfaction variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and co-workers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient. The job satisfaction variable shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and co-workers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient.

Based on the results of path analysis shows that leadership and work environment do not have an impact on increasing job satisfaction through motivation. This shows that motivation cannot mediate, namely leadership and work environment in influencing job satisfaction of employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV). The results of this study are not in line with the results of research conducted by Dewi Suryani Harahap, Hazmanan Khair (2019); Anak Agung Gede Dharma Saputra, Agoes Ganesha Rahyuda (2018).

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CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of research on the influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction through motivation at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), the following conclusions can be drawn:

Based on the results of the description analysis, regression analysis and path analysis, it is obtained that:

a. Leadership

Based on the description analysis on the leadership variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of analytical ability, communication skills, courage, listening ability and assertiveness make up the leadership variable. The indicator that dominates the formation of the leadership variable is the analytical ability indicator, namely the MNCTV leadership has high organizational analysis skills.

b. Work environment

Based on the description analysis of work environment variables, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the indicators of lighting/light in the workplace, air circulation at work, noise in the workplace, unpleasant odors in the workplace, and safety at work form work environment variables. The noise indicator in the workplace gives the greatest value to the formation of the work environment variable, namely the office where employees work far from vehicle noise.

c. Motivation

Based on the analysis of the description v of the job satisfaction variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and co-workers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient.

d. Job satisfaction

Based on the description analysis on the job satisfaction variable, it shows that employees at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) tend to agree that the work itself, salary/wages, supervision, and coworkers make up the variable job satisfaction. The indicator that gives the highest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary/wages, namely the salary received by MNCTV employees is sufficient.

Suggestion

Based on the results of research on the influence of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction through motivation at PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), some suggestions can be made as follows:

1. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the knowledge, insight and experience of researchers in the field of human resource management, especially regarding leadership, work environment, motivation and job satisfaction of employees in television broadcasting service companies and this research is expected to increase motivation and job satisfaction employees through constructive efforts to improve leadership and work environment.
2. The results of this study are expected to be used as input and reference for organizations to take policies or decisions that are deemed necessary in an effort to increase employee motivation and job satisfaction through efforts to improve leadership and the work environment, taking into account the following:

a. Leadership

In order to be a concern for PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), to pay attention to the firmness indicator that gives the lowest value to the formation of the leadership variable, namely the MNCTV leadership must have firmness in acting against employees who are not disciplined towards the organization by giving punishment.

b. Work environment

In order to be a concern for PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), to pay attention to the lighting indicator that gives the lowest value to the formation of the work environment variable, namely by the way the room where employees work must have good lighting so that employees can work comfortably.

c. Motivation

In order to be a concern for PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), to pay attention to the indicator of the need for power which gives the lowest value to the formation of the motivation variable, namely by giving all MNCTV employees the opportunity to have a career by looking at work competencies and the length of the employee's tenure.

d. Job satisfaction

In order to be a concern for PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV), to pay attention to the indicators of colleagues who give the

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lowest value to the formation of job satisfaction variables, namely by way of the leadership of PT CIPTA TPI (MNCTV) holding outings so that employees know each other all divisions and co-workers cooperate with each other other.

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